

Discrete Global Grid Systems (DGGS) for Geometrically Rigorous GeoAI

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Discrete Global Grid Systems

(DGGs) for Geometrically
Rigorous GeoAI

Is your GeoAI solving for Earth... or for flat maps?

Level 2

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GEOSPATIAL ANALYTICS, TECHNOLOGY AND OPEN RESEARCH

Geometry matters

Lines of true scale

UTM Scale Distortion

A pixel is not constant...
It represents varying geographic reality.

Models waste parameters on learning to unwarp projections, not learning geographic processes.

0.23% area discrepancy

- 10m pixels -> 0.23m² / pixel
- 100m pixels -> 23m² / pixel (~ shed)
- Adds up to 2,300m² / km²

The world has no “edges”

x

The world has no “edges”

We are forcing models to learn “wraparound” techniques, and implement clever tricks to solve a problem that doesn't exist on a sphere.

GeoAI *on* the Earth: DGGS (Discrete Global Grid Systems)

H3

<https://h3geo.org/>

ISEA4H

Ma et al. (2025)

<https://doi.org/10.3390/app15073703>

GeoAI on the

systems)

ISEA4H

- Metric stationarity
- Topological continuity
- Hierarchical, multi-scale efficiency
- Spatio-temporal persistence
- “Geodesic kernels”

**DGGS is not just
clever indexing.**

**It's the native,
geometrically rigorous
OS for Earth.**

<https://h3geo.org/>

[/app15073703](#)

A research agenda: Building rigorous GeoAI

- **Equal-area frameworks**
 - metric stationarity and translational equivariance
- **Benchmarking geodesic infrastructure**
 - understand properties, evaluate trade-offs
- **DGGS native data supply chain**
 - We need cloud-native formats that treat the sphere as native data structure
- **Resolving the hardware-software mismatch**
 - Geodesic kernels, CUDA operations, to eliminate the “computational tax” of forcing spherical data into flat memory

Let's think beyond the “shortcuts”

Discrete Global Grid Systems as a Framework for Geometrically Rigorous and Spatially Explicit GeoAI: A Research Agenda (Position Paper)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18471033>

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